

A self-powered asynchronous image sensor with TFS operation

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Abstract—This article presents a self-powered image sensor with a novel pixel architecture with energy harvesting capabilities. Pixels are autonomous entities that can harvest or sense illumination independently. Pixels have a fully asynchronous operation and do not require to be scanned to read out their asynchronous output. The sensor was manufactured in UMC 180nm technology and tested. Their specifications are competitive against the art, offering fast operation, good balance between the energy consumed and harvested, and high-dynamic range operation. The article describes the sensor and pixel architectures in detail and provides experimental results. Sensor specifications are benchmarked against the art.

Index Terms—Integrated photovoltaic cells, image sensor, self-powered, energy harvesting, stacked diodes, diode efficiency, asynchronous operation, Time-to-First-Spike.

I. INTRODUCTION

ENERGY-EFFICIENT sensors are the fuel to implement the Internet-of-Things paradigm and, ultimately, critical enablers of the cyber-universe of fully interconnected analog sensors and digital processors [1]. The International Roadmap for Devices and Semiconductors [2] identifies the reduction of the size, weight, and power of sensor nodes as major challenges for deploying distributed sensor networks in an ever-increasing number of applications involving interaction with the environment and hence analog signal sensing. Because optical images and the visual sense have a large quota among the different sensing modalities, it is arguable that energy-efficient vision sensors will play a relevant role in future Internet-of-Things (IoT) systems and intelligent electronic systems in general [1], [2]. Indeed, different strategic agendas identify the deployment of visual intelligence as one primary driver for disruption in information technologies and microsystem design [3].

The quest for energy-efficient vision sensors encompasses diverse challenges. On the one hand, vision chip concepts and architectures capable of capturing and analyzing images with

a minimum power budget are required. On the other hand, opportunities to harvest energy from the luminous stimuli must be explored. Reducing the power budget guarantees long working cycles under battery supply for low-latency applications. A reduced power budget besides energy harvesting might allow battery-less operation or very long battery-replacement cycles for high-latency applications.

The power reduction challenge calls for either the incorporation, at the focal plane, of embedded feature extraction and parallel processing resources [4] or for the use of asynchronous event-driven vision sensor concepts [5]–[7], among other strategies. The harvesting challenge calls for reconfiguring photodiodes to acquire either information or energy. Different image sensors combining both acquisition modes have been reported during the last few years - see [8]–[15] as representative examples. The vision sensor chip reported in this paper employs event-driven pixels operating in the Time-to-First-Spike (TFS) mode [16], [17] for information acquisition with reverse-biased photodiodes and the photovoltaic mode [18], [19] for energy harvesting.

Event-driven sensor concepts are particularly well suited for power-budget reduction. Unlike conventional, frame-based image sensors, event-driven ones do not aim at scanning and encoding the whole pixel array, despite the relevance of the local pixel information, but at locating and encoding only pixel data that convey relevant information. Hence, no energy is employed to encode and read irrelevant pixel data, thus making a significant difference from conventional imagers. Precluding such useless data encoding saves significant energy because ADC conversion and readout define the largest part of the imagers power budget [4]. Indeed, ADC converters are not required because pulses encode pixel information in the time

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domain; pixels send out pulses whenever they have relevant information to transmit. Besides their inherent power-saving properties, event-driven sensors have other unique capabilities for combining sensing and harvesting, namely:

- Pixels are autonomous entities, and hence they can start harvesting energy individually once they have sensed their local illumination.
- Their intrinsic asynchronous operation mode fits very well with application scenarios where snapshots are taken when an event occurs. For instance, the recognition of an intruder in surveillance systems [20], motion detection at home [21], traffic monitoring [22], or external operator-triggered scene luminance measurements [23].

Although several authors have already anticipated the advantages of using pulse-width modulation to information in self-powered pixels with shallow power consumption [11], [13], [24], there are very few self-powered asynchronous sensors reported so far. Shi and Bermak advanced a concept of an isolated asynchronous self-powered pixel [12]. However, to our knowledge, no contributions report self-powered asynchronous image sensors. In this article, we propose a novel, fully asynchronous sensor implementation. Its pixels are autonomous entities that can harvest energy once they have sensed their local illumination. Thus, pixels contribute to harvesting energy once their local illumination level is read out. The article provides experimental results and insights into the pixel and sensor architecture. The proposed pixel architecture is the first one that allows different pixels to harvest energy or sense illumination independently and has not been reported yet. The image sensor is benchmarked against the art showing the advantages of the proposed architecture.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system is composed of two different blocks, as shown in Fig. 1. The first of them is a low-power asynchronous vision sensor, which combines the tasks of sensing and energy harvesting. The harvested energy is stored in a 7.5 mF low leakage off-chip supercapacitor, $C_{storage}$, designed for energy harvesting applications [25]. During the energy harvesting phase, the photodiodes are connected in parallel, charging the supercapacitor, whose voltage, V_{EH} , is limited by the illumination conditions. This supercapacitor performs the function of a charge reservoir, with a reduced footprint of 3.2 mm × 2.5 mm. Although the pixels of the vision sensor are designed to operate with a supply voltage as low as 250 mV, delay in the readout chain can generate artifacts in the image. Therefore, a dedicated DC-DC converter is included in the same die to step up the voltage at V_{EH} . Fig. 2 shows a microphotograph of the die containing both blocks.

The operation of the system is divided into two different phases. During the harvesting phase, the sensor is in idle state, and all photodiodes operate in photovoltaic mode. In this mode, a current I_{pv} flows from the cathode to the anode, and a voltage V_{pv} builds up at the junction, as depicted in Fig. 3. The collected charge is stored in the supercapacitor. Since power consumption is not continuous and the system does not have an external battery beyond the supercapacitor, no maximum power point tracking technique [26] was

implemented. Therefore, the choice of a high capacitance allows storing a large amount of energy when the sensor is exposed to high illumination. When the system demands information from the scene, the sensing phase starts. During this phase, the photodiodes of the pixels are reverse biased and operate in TFS mode to measure the photocurrent. One major novelty of this sensor lies in how the pixels work after readout. The pixels stop consuming energy and start harvesting energy immediately after they send the information to the external receiver. In this way, the most illuminated pixels support the sensing operation. However, the supply voltage drops during the sensing operation, limiting the frame rate of the sensor by the time the DC-DC requires to regulate the supply voltage. This voltage drop depends on the time the pixels are consuming energy, and therefore on the scene.

A. Harvesting subsystem

The core components of the harvesting subsystem are the photodiodes of the pixel. The cathode of the photodiode is connected to ground when the pixel operates in harvesting mode. Thus, the photocurrent leaving the anode (see Fig. 3) is used to charge the reservoir. Fig. 3 encloses four parameters. First, I_{sc} is the short-circuit current, i.e., the current at 0 V. The voltage when no current flows through the junction is called the open-circuit voltage, V_{oc} , and it is the maximum voltage that can be generated keeping the diode reverse biased. If the junction voltage is greater than V_{oc} , it is forward biased and consumes energy. Finally, there is a maximum power point, defined by I_{mpp} and V_{mpp} .

Photodiodes are usually connected in series to increase the effective value of V_{oc} . These branches of photodiodes are then connected in parallel to increase the available power; however, standard CMOS processes do not allow series association of photodiodes without penalty [27], [28]. Although other authors proposed a series connection of two diodes with different active areas to reduce parasitic current leakage [29], this approach is process-dependent and difficult to predict analytically. Thus, an only-parallel photodiode array is usually preferred, at the cost of a maximum V_{oc} close to 500 mV [18]. Photodiode stacking can also be employed to slightly increase V_{oc} [18], but still DC-DC conversion might be necessary to power a real system [19].

Fig. 4 (a) shows the schematic of the DC-DC converter core. Under typical indoor illumination conditions, the voltage of the harvesting node, V_{EH} , is set close to 250 mV and the DC-DC converter steps up this voltage to 700 mV. The core is composed of a classic three-stage Dickson DC-DC converter. In this implementation, the well of the PMOS transistors is connected to the drain to reduce the reverse current [30]. The output of the DC-DC converter is connected to an off-chip 100 μ F capacitor to reduce the voltage drop during operation. Furthermore, since the input voltage level can be below 250 mV, the converter also includes a clock voltage doubler to ensure that the converter works under low illumination conditions. Fig. 4 (b) shows the schematic of the voltage doubler, where Φ and $\bar{\Phi}$ are the clock and inverted clock phases, respectively. The frequency of the clock is controlled

Fig. 1: Sensor architecture. The main constitute blocks are: the pixel array, external buffers and control circuitry, external asynchronous arbitration logic to implement the AER communication protocol, and a Dickson DC-DC converter.

Fig. 2: Chip microphotograph. The yellow dotted line contains the image sensor. Pixel-level detail is shown. The red dotted line the DC-DC converter. The image sensor dimensions are $2800 \text{ mm} \times 2800 \text{ mm}$. Pixel Dickson DC-DC converter dimensions, including the capacitor array, are $2430 \text{ mm} \times 1040 \text{ mm}$.

off-chip, since the voltage regulation of this converter was not included in this implementation. Thus, energy management still needs to be optimized in future implementations.

B. Vision sensor

The vision sensor employs a standard Address Event Representation (AER) protocol [31]–[34] to support asynchronous readout. Fig. 1 shows the block diagram of the vision sensor. In addition to the pixel array, the sensor is composed of column and row buffers followed by 0.3 V to 1.8 V level shifters (in case the peripheral circuitry is biased at a voltage higher than the pixel array), AER communication logic blocks, 7-bit encoders and row and column arbiter trees [34].

Fig. 3: I-V curve of a photodiode operating in photovoltaic regime. The black arrow indicates how the curves vary with the illumination.

When a pixel generates an event, the X and Y arbiter trees decide which pixel accesses the address bus, while the AER communication logic blocks generate two global signals, req_y and req_x . The AND operation of both signals, bus_req indicates to the receiver that the pixel corresponding to the address bus coordinates has generated an event. This bus is composed of the output of the encoders, $addr_x$ and $addr_y$. Finally, when the external peripheral has read and stored the pixel address, the external receiver activates bus_ack and the AER communication logic blocks generate the signals that reset the pixel.

Furthermore, two 128-bit shift registers store the enable sequence in such a way that the pix_on and $reset$ signals are only enabled in certain rows and columns. This allows a ROI to sense the lighting level and keep the rest of the pixels harvesting energy.

Fig. 4: a) 3-stage PMOS Dickson charge pump. b) Clk voltage doubler. All transistor dimensions are $\frac{W(\mu m)}{L(\mu m)} = \frac{100}{0.2}$.

III. PROPOSED PIXEL

Fig. 5 shows the schematic of the pixel, where V_{EH} is the global storage node shared among pixels. The pixel has been designed at the electrical level to operate with 250 mV supply voltage so that its operation is directly compatible with the voltage levels generated by the pixel array. Pixels are autonomous entities that can harvest energy from the environment while not sensing the illumination level. This is controlled by the signal stored in the per-pixel SR latch. Depending on the output of the latch, transistors M_{p1-2} and M_{n1-2} commute the terminals of the photodiode [35]. When the photodiode is reverse biased, a comparator and pull-down transistors implement the TFS operation an AER communication.

A. Photodiode layout and configurations

A description of diode implementation was advanced in a preliminary conference contribution [35]. As already mentioned, diodes toggle between two operation regimes: Photo-voltaic and reverse biased regime. The top view and the cross section of the photodiode are shown in Fig. 6, where three different diodes are connected in parallel, namely the n^+ / P-well junction, D1, the P-well/Deep N-well junction, D2, and the Deep N-well/p-sub junction, D3. The three diodes share the same cathode. The anodes of D1 and D2 are also shared, and the anode of D3 is grounded; therefore, D3 cannot contribute to energy harvesting. It has previously been demonstrated that the architecture including D1 and D2 in parallel presents a higher open-circuit voltage than non-stacked diodes [18]. An interesting aspect introduced in this implementation is that the cathodes of D1 and D2 are connected extending the n^+ diffusion of D1. This allows to increase the active area of D1 and the pixel fill factor.

The configuration of the photodiode depends on the state of the pixel, which is defined by the local *lock* signal. When *lock* is deactivated (and, therefore, \overline{lock} activated), the photodiode is reverse biased and a current can flow from the power supply node, V_{DD} , to ground through the photodiode, as depicted in Fig.7 (a). In contrast, when *lock* is logic high, the cathode is grounded, and the photodiode enters the photovoltaic regime to harvest energy immediately after readout. In this configuration, the photocurrent flows to the V_{EH} node, thus contributing to the power supply, as shown in Fig.7 (b).

The proper electrical design of M_{n3} and M_{p4} is crucial. In order to operate at supply voltages close to 250 mV, thin-gate-oxide transistors were selected. These two transistors must be strong enough to drive a current larger than the photocurrent, I_{ph} , when the pixel is under high-illumination conditions; however, the leakage current, I_{leak} , increases with the strength of the switch, leading to a random offset and therefore, pixel-to-pixel nonuniformities. Although I_{leak} can reduce the dynamic range, its effect can be alleviated by an off-chip calibration process.

B. Pixel operation

The pixels rely on the TFS concept to sense the illumination level of the scene. TFS operation is particularly interesting as the brightest pixels are readout first. Therefore, they instantly contribute to energy harvesting, while the less illuminated ones consume energy. The operation is governed by *pix_on*, which is defined as the AND operation of two signals, *pix_on_h*, and *pix_on_v*. These signals are shared per row and per column, respectively, and are the output of the AND operation of the global *pix_on* signal and the sequence stored in the shift registers from Fig. 1. This allows the system to enable only a region of interest (ROI), while the rest of the pixels are harvesting energy.

The different signals involved in the operation of the pixels are represented in Fig.8. Before starting the sensing operation, *pix_on* is logic-low and *rst_pix* is logic-high. Thus, *lock* is activated at the beginning of the operation. At this point, the operation can be divided into three phases:

1) **Reset:** To sense the pixel illuminance, the charge is integrated in the photodiode capacitance, C_{ph} . Therefore, the photodiode must be reset at the beginning of the operation. This is accomplished by the active-low *rst_pix* signal and transistor M_{p4} . Note that this signal also unlocks the pixel. To prevent M_{p4} from driving a current in pixels outside the ROI, *rst_pix* is implemented as the NAND function of *pix_on* and a global *reset* signal:

$$rst_pix = \overline{pix_on \cdot reset} \quad (1)$$

In this way, when the *pix_on* signal is logic high, *rst_pix* is the negated value of *reset*. The reset time, t_{rst} , must be minimized to reduce power consumption, though this time must be long enough to reset high-illuminated photodiodes.

2) **Integration:** When *reset* is released, the voltage at node V_n decreases linearly depending on the photocurrent value. Defining T_{int} as the time it takes the photodiode to reach the

Fig. 5: Pixel schematics. It is composed of a photodiode and two pair of switches, a comparator, pull-down transistors, a memory cell and reset and enable logic. Transistors dimensions $\frac{W}{L} (\mu\text{m})$ are: $M_{n1-2} = 0.44/0.4$, $M_{p1-2} = 0.5/0.4$, $M_{n4-7} = 5.7/0.18$.

Fig. 6: a) Photodiode top view. b) Photodiode cross-section including the three P-N junctions: $n^+/p\text{well}$ (D1), $p\text{-well}/dnw$ (D2) and $dnw/psub$ (D3).

voltage threshold of the comparator, V_{th} , the photocurrent can be computed as:

$$I_{ph,TFS} = C_{ph} \cdot \frac{(V_{DD} - V_{th})}{T_{int}} \quad (2)$$

It is important to note that the measurement depends on the value of V_{DD} . This value is the same for all pixels, but may vary from frame to frame. Thus, if the application requires computing information among different measurements, this voltage must be properly regulated.

3) Readout: When V_n reaches V_{th} , the output of the comparator, *spike*, indicates that the pixel must be read out. To do so, the pixel uses transistors M_{n4-7} . First, the series combination of M_{n4} and M_{n6} pulls down $\overline{req_row}$. This signal is shared by the entire row, implementing a wired OR gate. An arbiter circuit decides which row must be read

Fig. 7: Photodiode configuration when it is a) sensing b) harvesting.

and activates the $\overline{ack_row}$ signal, so pixels in that row can pull down the $\overline{req_col}$ signal and repeat the process at the column level. After granting access to the pixel, the AER communication logic block activates *bus_req* to indicate that valid data is set on the output address bus. Finally, the receiver stores the coordinates of the pixel and activates *bus_ack*. This signal triggers $\overline{rst_col}$ and $\overline{rst_row}$, so that the local *ack_pix* signal locks the pixel.

Fig. 8: Chronogram of the signals involved in the pixel's operation.

Fig. 9: Schematic of the pixel comparator. Transistors dimensions $\frac{W(\mu m)}{L(\mu m)}$ are: $M_{p,b} = 7.04/0.4$, $M_{p1} = M_{p2} = 3.52/0.18$, $M_{n1} = M_{n2} = 0.88/2$, $M_{n,en} = M_{p,en} = 0.88/0.3$, $M_{p3} = M_{p4} = M_{n3} = M_{n4} = 0.44/0.3$.

C. Comparator

Fig. 9 shows the schematic of the in-pixel comparator. It is the only analog block and the dominant source of power consumption. Thus, a careful design of this component is crucial for proper performance. The comparator is composed of a 5T-OTA followed by a CMOS inverter, as depicted in Fig. 9. The comparator is designed to work at supply voltages as low as 250 mV and all transistors work in weak inversion to reduce the power consumption of the entire array, at the expense of a reduced speed. When the pixel is harvesting energy, $M_{n,en}$ switches off the bias current of the comparator using the *lock* control signal.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 10: Measured short-circuit current and open-circuit voltage of photodiodes versus illuminance at $T=30$ °C

Fig. 11: Sample image rendered with the sensor of a scene with 60 dB intra-scene dynamic range.

A. Open-circuit voltage

Fig. 10 shows the dependence between the short-circuit current and the open-circuit voltage with illumination. Both parameters determine the sensor's capability to harvest energy. Given an illumination value, V_{EH} tends to reach the open-circuit voltage. The V_{oc} voltage has a logarithmic dependence on illumination and decreases linearly with temperature [18]. The short-circuit current determines the speed at which energy can be harvested. Thus, the parameter affects the effective sensor frame rate, i.e., the number of snapshots per time unit rendered without using an external power supply.

B. Dynamic power consumption and energy harvesting

In Fig. 11, an image captured with the sensor is shown. The measured intra-dynamic range was 62 dB. A colormap was used to represent the illumination values. The image was acquired in 14 ms. Fig. 12 depicts experimental data showing

Fig. 12: Top panel: Number of pixels operating in sensing mode during the acquisition of the image shown in Fig. 11. Bottom panel: Balance between the sensor power consumption and the power harvested by the pixels operating in harvesting mode during the image acquisition.

the amount of energy consumed and harvested by the sensor during the previous image acquisition. Fig. 12 (top panel) shows the percentage of pixels operating in sensing and harvesting mode during the image acquisition. Initially, all pixels start in sensing mode. Then, the most illuminated pixels toggle to harvesting mode and begin to harvest energy. In Fig. 12 (bottom panel), the measured energy consumed and the estimated energy harvested are plotted. Two situations have been considered to estimate the harvested energy: operating with an ideal Dickson DC-DC converter and with the implemented converter with an efficiency of $\eta = 60\%$. The sensor harvests the energy required to acquire the image in 17 ms. Analyzing the plots, we can conclude that the maximum energy that the sensor consumes when all pixels operate in sensing mode is higher than the maximum amount of energy collected when all pixels harvest energy simultaneously. Thus, the sensor cannot operate continuously and needs to harvest energy between acquisitions. In the example, an effective frame rate of 58 fps was achieved with self-powering operation.

C. Acquisition time versus illumination

According to the experimental results of Fig. 12, the energy harvested is higher than that consumed during the image acquisition time. Operating without an external power supply is a factor that limits the effective frame rate. After acquiring a frame (or a sequence of frames), it is necessary to pre-charge the battery that feeds the sensor before starting the acquisition of a new frame (or a sequence of them). Fig. 13 depicts experimental data showing the maximum possible frame rate versus the illuminance. The maximum frame rate is determined by the frame acquisition and the frame readout time. All pixels were exposed to the same illumination level. When the sensor external battery is pre-charged, 60 frames per second (fps) can be recorded with a chip illuminance of only 10 lux. It must be remarked that the energy balance is quite complex for visual scenes with a large intra-scene dynamic range, with high

Fig. 13: Measured maximum frame rate versus illumination. All pixels were illuminated uniformly. The maximum frame rate is determined by the sum of the image acquisition and readout time.

Fig. 14: Measured sensor outputs (DN) versus illumination over six decades. The red line indicate the linear data fitting. The coefficient of determination is $r^2 = 0.9370$

and low illuminated pixels. In such cases, an acquisition time can be defined to read out the image, trading between image quality and speed depending on the application scenario. Fast acquisition penalties low illuminated pixels.

D. Pixel response to illumination and FPN

Fig. 14 shows the measured sensor output versus the chip illuminance. All pixels were illuminated uniformly with a white Lambertian light source. The red trace corresponds with the linear data fitting. The coefficient of determination is $r^2 = 0.9370$. The sensor response to illumination is linear within an illumination range of four decades. Below 10 lux the sensor output linearity is limited by the current leakage

TABLE I: State-of-the-art comparison.

Features Work	This work	Tang 2011 [36]	Park 2018 [10]	Chiou 2016 [11]	Cevik 2015 [8]	H.Wang 2015 [37]
Pixel Architecture	Asynchronous pixel with TFS readout	APS pixel with synchronous readout	APS pixel with synchronous readout	Synchronous pixel with PWM readout	APS pixel with synchronous readout	Synchronous pixel with ADC readout
Technology	UMC 0.18 μm	0.35 μm	0.18 μm	0.18 μm	0.35 μm	0.5 μm
Pixel complexity	54 Transistors	4 Transistors	3 Transistors	5 Transistors	4 Transistors	14 transistors
Pixel Count	128 \times 128	128 \times 96	100 \times 90	256 \times 192	64 \times 45	32 \times 32
Fill factor (%)	30.65	39	46 / 94 ^a	30.8	65	36
Pixel Pitch	19.5 μm	21 μm	5 μm	7.5 μm	18 μm	54 μm \times 48 μm
Supply Voltage	0.7 V	1.35 V	0.6 V	0.32 V	1 V	ND
Pixel Power Consumption	70 pW	30.7 pW	ND	ND	ND	ND
Sensor Power Consumption	1.14 μW	10 μW	3.9-57.8 μW	10.6 μW	9.06 μW	ND
Frame rate for the reported sensor power consumption (fps)	51.5fps@500lux, 19.9fps@100lux	9.6	7.5-10	6.5	21.2	ND
Dynamic Range	100 dB	ND	ND	137 dB	60.6 dB	ND
FPN (%)	5.34	>1	9.2	0.189	0.33	ND
iFoM (fJ/pixel-code)	3.41	164.06	225.8	8.6	578	3304.7
Independent Energy harvesting and light sensing operation	Yes (at pixel level)	No	No	No	No	Yes (configurable)

^aThe pixel has two stacked photodiodes. Results are reported for the photodiode used to sense light and the one used to harvest energy, respectively.

introduced by the transistors connected to the anode and cathode of the photodiode in Fig. 5. This leakage is comparable to the photocurrent with low illumination and is responsible for the sensor non-linearity in such circumstances. The current leakage also impacts the Fixed-Pattern-Noise (FPN) of the pixels with low illumination because the leakage current has a large variability from pixel to pixel. The measured FPN was 5.34% with a sensor illuminance of 1 klux. This limitation could be amended by using transistors with a thicker gate oxide. Sensor calibration is also possible to improve image quality. The procedure can be performed off-chip by subtracting the illumination values measured without illumination to each frame.

V. BENCHMARKING

Table I compares the specifications of the implemented sensor against other relevant and recent self-powered ones. The proposed architecture is the only one compatible with simultaneous harvesting and image acquisition at the pixel level. This possibility optimizes the amount of energy harvested because the most illuminated pixels have an earlier and higher contribution to the sensor's self-powered operation. Moreover, the proposed asynchronous readout allows dynamically deciding the amount of time dedicated to acquiring one image. It is possible to render one image after receiving a certain number of events or update the image representation

dynamically. Therefore, there is room for further research work to investigate the optimal balance between integration time, image quality, and power consumption.

The proposed architecture outperforms the art, offering a very low image acquisition and readout time, exploiting the advantages of the fast asynchronous readout circuitry. Frames can be acquired within a short time interval. Therefore, the ratio between the amount of time the sensor is harvesting and sensing is higher than in previous implementations. Even if we consider a continuous sensor operation, powering the sensor externally, the pixel energy consumption is competitive over the art. The sensor also offers high intra-scene dynamic range operation. The main limitation of the proposed architecture is the FPN level, which is higher than the art. This can be amended in further implementations by performing a careful study to reduce the current leakage of the transistors that alters the photocurrent measurement. At this point, there is room for improvement by selecting different types of transistors or simplifying the number of transistors connected to the photodiode.

Furthermore, the functionalities of the sensor can be extended to implement a Free Running mode. In this mode, pixels are reset after readout and events are generated continuously. Therefore, the temporal error caused by the collisions is averaged. However, pixels are continuously consuming energy during this mode, limiting its use to periods when

the average illumination is high enough. To implement this function, switches must be added to V_p to keep the photodiode reverse biased regardless of *lock* and a reset logic must be implemented to reset the pixel when *lock* is activated.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A new self-powered asynchronous image sensor has been presented. The proposed architecture amends some of the limitations of classic synchronous pixel architectures to harvest energy. On one hand, pixels are autonomous entities that can harvest energy or sense illumination independently, not being necessary to divide the sensor operation into two phases associated with energy harvesting and sensing. On the other hand, the proposed asynchronous readout scheme proves to be very competitive to harvest energy because there is no requirement for an A/D conversion or to read out all the pixels to render one image. With the proposed sensor architecture, the system can trade between image quality, frame rate, and power consumption. All of these capabilities open the possibility for further research work to optimize sensor operation and the amount of energy harvested depending on the illumination conditions and image rendering requirements.

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